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Valuation of Sensex 30 Companies

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Abstract

At the time of buying decision one should interested in knowing which companies survive for the long run and earn tones and tones of wealth for the investors. This survival is based on the competitive advantage enjoyed by the organizations. There are various threats to the business survival given under Porter's five forces framework. These are Suppliers, Customers, Substitutes, New Entrants and Competitors. Business has to deal with these forces on day to day basis. So, investor should find the positioning of the business in the market.

Keywords Sensex, BCG matrix, PE ratio.

Introduction

With the help of BCG matrix given by Boston Consulting Group investors can identify companies whose market share is high as well as growth rate is also high. One can invest in these types of companies at the time of market corrections or when the multiples are in the range. Price earnings ratio of the company is affected by the multiple of factors. A company whose growth rate is high get high PE ratio in the market. PE ratio is affected by the several factors such as interest rates, inflation expectations, growth rate, ROIIC, tax rates, equity risk premium, cyclical fluctuations and bull and bear trends in the economy (Mauboussin, 2014). So, one has to invest at right PE to get their money grow in future. While investing in any stock PE ratio can be taken as industry average or the company specific average PE. The other way to find the PE of the company is to find out maintenance capital expenditure or reinvestment rate of the company taking into consideration the profit growth of the company and return on invested capital.

$$\text{Reinvestment Rate} = \text{Profit Growth} / \text{Return on invested Capital}$$

Thus, profit left after maintenance capital expenditure or reinvestment rate is the real profit available to be distributed to the equity share holders of the company. This profit should be used to calculate the PE of the company (Steven, 2019). Maintenance capital expenditure determines company is burning cash or company is generating free cash flows which will be available to be distributed to the equity share holders of the company. As per rule of 72 at 7 % interest rate of fixed deposits money is doubled in 10 years. After Covid 19, market show a one way rally and Nifty 50 Index is 3 Times (8000 to 24000) from 2020 low's and 2 Times (12000 to 24000) if we take the index before Covid 19 pandemic. In current times, valuations of the companies are sky rocketing due to one way rally in last 5 years (2020 to 2024). So, the problem in front of small investors is how to choose or select companies for investment in such high valuation environment where investment managers also waiting for market corrections to deploy more money in the share market. Current Market Price of any stock is the multiplication of PE x EPS. Stock price increases when either PE ratio increases or the Earnings of the company increases. So, investor should make investments in such companies when there is scope of earnings growth as well as PE expansion (Mayer, 2015). In this research paper, author will make a comparison of Sensex 30 companies by the use of Pay Back Period and Price Earnings Growth Ratios to identify current value parameters of those companies and to find best companies for investments.

Objective of study

1. To identify the Price Earnings Growth Ratio of Sensex 30 Companies.
2. To study the relationship between Payback Period and Future Expected Earnings.
3. To compare the companies on the basis of these financial ratios.

4. To find out the companies those are favorable for the Investments.

Review of Literature

Sensex constitute well diversified 30 Large Cap Companies Listed on Bombay Stock Exchange. It includes stock from various sectors of the economy. The base value of Sensex was taken as 100 on 1st April 1979 and its base year as 1978-79. In February 2025 Sensex reached 73000 points. Sensex multiplied 730 times in 45 Years from its base value. As per Warrant Buffet, the value of stock is the present value of future free cash flows from the business. Pablo Farnandez and Aswath Damodaran also advocate for the use of discounted free cash flow method but at the same time they agree that 90 to 95 percent of the valuations are based on multiples or relative valuation methods. When we use DCF method it is not easy to forecast uncertain, uneven and fluctuating cash flows and also the use of accurate discount rate, growth rate and terminal value is a puzzle for small investors. A small error in assumption leads to absurd results. Sometime cash flows are negative for a long period of time. Multiples based valuation methods are easy to use and less time consuming. Company valuation methods are broadly classified into absolute valuation methods and relative valuation methods. Absolute valuation methods are company specific and relative valuation methods compares the multiples of the companies with the similar companies. There are several ratios used in valuation methods for making quick comparison. It includes EV to EBITDA Method , Price Earning Growth (PEG) Ratio, Price to Book Value (PB/V) Ratio, Price Earnings (PE) Ratio, Return on Equity (ROE) Method, Return on Capital Employed (ROCE), Dividend Yield Ratio, Price to Sales Ratio, Price to Cash Flow Ratio, Pay Back Period etc (Tulsian, 2009). Relative valuation methods compare the company value to other similar firms. EV to EBITDA ratio is calculated by dividing the enterprise value of the company from EBITDA of the company. Price earnings ratio is calculated by dividing the market price of the company from the Earning per Share of the company. Price Earning Growth ratio is calculated by dividing the PE of the company from the estimated earnings growth of the company. Price to book value is calculated by dividing current market price per share from the book value per share. Earnings per share are calculated by dividing the net profits of the company by the number of outstanding shares of the company. Return on equity is calculated by dividing the Net Profit of the company from the Shareholders Equity. Return on Capital Employed is calculated by dividing the Earnings before Interest and Tax from the total capital employed in the business. Dividend Yield is calculated by dividing the Dividend per Share from the Market Price per Share of the company. Market cap to sales ratio is calculated by dividing the market capitalization of the company from the total sales of the company. Price to operating cash flow ratio is calculated by dividing market price per share from the operating cash flow per share. Pay Back period refers to the period within which the entire cost of the project is expected to be completely recovered by way of cash inflows. Payback period is calculated by dividing the market capitalization of the company from the total of 5 years expected net profits. If payback period is one or less than one, it will be an investment opportunity (Agrawal, 2014). These ratios are used by the fund managers for investing in the shares of the companies. Companies are broadly classified into large cap companies, mid cap companies and small cap companies. Movement and fluctuations in the small and mid cap companies are higher than small cap companies. Sensex includes 30 large cap companies known as blue chip companies of India. Companies are different in nature, size and composition. Some are cyclical and some are secular. Some companies are capital intensive and require heavy debt whereas other companies require low debt in their capital structure. Some companies give dividends whereas some pay no dividends. Some companies are value companies and others are growth companies. Some companies generating positive cash flows whereas other companies are not generating positive cash flows. Some companies are consistent compounders and predictable earnings growth whereas others are volatiles. These companies' share prices are influenced by both internal and external influences. Internal factor includes sales, net profits, growth rate, change of management and Debt in the Capital Structure of that company. External factor includes change in government policies and regulation for a particular sector, subsidy and up and down cycles in India and World economy. Investment manager across different AMC's varies in their investment styles. Some are Value investors where as other are growth investors. Price of the stock is known to everyone, but what is the underlying value of share, the intrinsic value and margin of safety in that stock is the matter of skills and expertise. Investment managers use different company valuation methods to find out the underlying value of these stocks. In this research paper I am using Payback Period and PEG ratio to analyze 30 stocks listed in BSE Sensex.

Methodology

Five year expected net profits from 2026 to 2030 of the Sensex 30 companies calculated using compounded average growth rate of net profits of these companies' from 2020 to 2025. Companies making losses due to their cyclical nature or showing abnormal growth rates during the period from 2020 to 2025 has been taken at industry average growth rates. While calculating net profit for the year ending 2024-2025, TTM net profit has been taken to provide cushion in valuation. Payback Period is calculated by dividing the market capitalization of the company from the expected accumulated 5 years net profits of the company. If the Payback Period is one or less than one it indicates that whole

market capitalization of the company, paid by the investor upfront will be covered from the net profits of the company in next 5 years and gains from the rest of the life of the business is the profit for the investor. PEG ratio is calculated by dividing the PE of the company from the expected earnings growth of the company. PEG ratio one or less than one indicate that company growth in earnings is higher than the number of times shares is quoted in the market in comparison to its earnings. Correlation between futures expected earnings and payback period has been tested through Pearson's Correlation using SPSS software.

Analysis

Sensex includes 30 large cap blue chip companies from different sectors of the economy. The risk of failure is less in these blue chip companies. Thus, investors and fund managers find a safe bet by investing in Sensex 30 companies of India. Investment in Sensex 30 companies is also done through Index Mutual Funds and Sensex 30 Exchange Traded Funds (ETF's). Table 1 indicates the various financial ratios such as price to book value ratio, price earnings ratio, price earnings growth ratio, EV to EBITDA ratio and price to cash flow ratio of companies listed in Sensex. A comparison of multiples has been drawn to find the value parameters of these companies. As per the PEG ratio, Bajaj Finance, State Bank of India, HDFC Bank, Kotak Mahindra Bank, Tata Motors, ICICI Bank, Axis Bank and Bharti Airtel showing a PEG ratio one or less than one. The P/E ratio of State Bank of India and Tata Motors is less than 10 when Sensex average PE is around 30. This indicates that State Bank of India and Tata Motors valuation are on lower side in comparison to Sensex 30 companies of India. Price to operating cash flow of Tata Motors, Power Grid and ICICI bank is between three to six times represents healthy cash flows of the company. Calculation of Payback Period has been shown in Table number 2. When we analyzed Payback period of these companies we found that State Bank of India, Tata Motors and Axis Bank Payback Period is one or less than one. Payback Period one or less than one indicate attractive opportunity for investment.

Pearson's correlation has been applied for data analysis. Future expected earnings have been taken as independent variable and payback period has been taken as dependent variable. Out of Sensex 30 companies 29 companies has been taken for the analysis. Zomato is making losses and recent listing thus it has been excluded from the analysis. When we saw the relationship between Payback Period and Future Expected Earnings we found that higher future expected earnings reduces the Payback period. Correlation between future expected earnings and payback period is -0.547.

Correlations

		Future Expected Earnings	Payback Period
Future Expected Earnings	Pearson Correlation	1	-.547(**)
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.002
	N	29	29
Payback Period	Pearson Correlation	-.547(**)	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002	
	N	29	29

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

This means that higher future expected earnings reduces the payback period. Thus we can say that there is significant negative relationship between futures expected earnings and payback period. Thus, our null hypothesis is rejected at 1% level of significance and alternate hypothesis is accepted and we can say that there is significant relationship between futures expected earnings and payback period. Our test result shows that correlation coefficient between future expected earnings and payback period is 54.70%. The proportion of variance (R^2) in the payback period that can be explained by the future expected earnings is 29.90 percent.

Conclusion

1. Pay Back Period one or less than one is favorable for investment.
2. Stock with less than 10 PE is good for investment when Index PE is 20 or 30.
3. Price to Cash Flow less than five times is favorable for investment.
4. EV to EBITDA less than five times is favorable for investment.
5. Price to Book value less than one is good for investment when company showing higher earnings growth and return ratios.
6. Price earnings growth ratio less than one indicate that earnings growth rate of the company is higher than its PE.

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Appendix

S. No.	Name of Company	P/BV	P/E	PEG	EV/EBITDA	P/CF
1	Bajaj Finance	6.21	33.80	1.15	18.40	-7.28
2	SBI	1.34	7.71	0.08	3.13	28.40
3	Titan	28.00	84.20	4.16	49.90	162.00
4	HDFC Bank	2.88	19.00	0.18	15.60	69.40
5	Infosys	7.94	25.40	2.26	15.90	27.80
6	Kotak Mahindra Bank	2.91	19.20	0.94	15.80	24.10
7	Reliance	1.98	23.50	1.96	10.40	10.20
8	Tata Steel	1.90	60.50	-10.40	9.75	8.44
9	L&T	4.88	31.40	3.84	15.30	23.80
10	M&M	4.56	26.00	1.54	13.00	-57.10
11	Tata Motors	2.26	7.18	0.08	4.70	3.36
12	Hindustan Uniliver	10.2	49.70	4.69	32.30	33.30
13	Nestle India	52.9	67.30	3.44	44.10	50.60
14	Asian Paints	11.6	47.90	2.34	29.80	34.30
15	ITC	6.57	24.90	2.47	16.90	28.80
16	Sun Pharma	5.53	32.40	1.39	22.70	31.50
17	ICICI Bank	3.30	17.30	0.29	14.90	5.41
18	Indusind Bank	1.23	10.70	1.23	12.30	-4.58
19	Axis Bank	2.00	11.20	0.28	14.00	-56.60
20	HCL Tech	6.21	25.00	2.70	15.00	19.00
21	Bharti Airtel	10.3	47.00	0.38	12.60	11.40
22	Maruti	4.21	25.80	1.46	14.70	22.40
23	Ultratech Cement	4.77	46.80	1.96	23.90	26.80
24	TCS	12.4	25.80	3.15	17.50	28.40
25	NTPC	1.79	13.70	2.01	9.05	7.40
26	Tech Mahindra	5.51	38.90	-3.46	19.60	22.80
27	Power Grid	2.53	15.00	1.77	8.53	6.26
28	Adani Ports	4.04	21.90	1.29	14.40	15.40
29	Bajaj Finserv	4.38	34.90	1.77	12.80	-4.35
30	Zomato	10.00	323.00	20.20	135.00	332.00

Table 2 - Calculation of Pay Back Period on the Basis of 5 Year Expected Net Profits					
S. No.	Name of Companies	Market Cap.	5 Year Expected Accumulated Profits		Pay Back Period Mkt. Cap/Accumulated Expected Net Profits
			28-Feb-25	From 2026 to 2030	
1	Bajaj Finance	539400.00		164738.00	3.27
2	SBI	617004.00		844763.00	0.73
3	Titan	272617.00		25093.00	10.86
4	HDFC Bank	1325385.00		644448.00	2.06
5	Infosys	701042.00		189895.00	3.69
6	Kotak Mahindra Bank	378138.00		201187.00	1.88
7	Reliance	1623410.00		632904.00	2.57
8	Tata Steel	171323.00		19587.00	8.75
9	L&T	435188.00		110612.00	3.93
10	M&M	321399.00		126405.00	2.54
11	Tata Motors	228560.00		320217.00	0.71
12	Hindustan Uniliver	514605.00		82988.00	6.20
13	Nestle India	211122.00		22575.00	9.35
14	Asian Paints	209077.00		30474.00	6.86
15	ITC	494052.00		137223.00	3.60
16	Sun Pharma	382407.00		102419.00	3.73
17	ICICI Bank	851147.00		537723.00	1.58
18	Indusind Bank	77164.00		48517.00	1.59
19	Axis Bank	314568.00		290623.00	1.08
20	HCL Tech	426879.00		114729.00	3.72
21	Bharti Airtel	939984.00		241758.00	3.89
22	Maruti	375458.00		129842.00	2.89
23	Ultratech Cement	293169.00		41680.00	7.03
24	TCS	1260340.00		329095.00	3.83
25	NTPC	301955.00		172807.00	1.75
26	Tech Mahindra	145732.00		25344.00	5.75
27	Power Grid	233397.00		138808.00	1.68
28	Adani Ports	231123.00		89764.00	2.57
29	Bajaj Finservice	299098.00		150784.00	1.98
30	Zomato	214278.00		6792.00	31.55